

Portable and flexible Framework for In-Memory Data Packaging and Transfer

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Abstract

We present a portable and flexible framework for transferring large amounts of scientific data. Its main objective is to prepare the data for transfer (e.g., tar, compress, encrypt, compute and verify hash), while delegating the network transfer to established external utilities. The framework is based on the pipeline approach, i.e., the transferred data stream is passed through a sequence of pipeline elements (or ‘filters’), which process the data and forward it downstream. The computations are done on the fly, hence there is no need for extra storage to archive and otherwise process the data. Compute-intensive tasks (e.g., compression, hash computations, encryption) are executed in parallel with the network transfer, which decreases the overall execution time of the workflow. The framework is implemented in Python3, it is portable, and easy to extend: individual pipeline elements are similar to Python’s file-like objects. We provide a general-purpose stager application driven by configuration files, and a Python API, which we use to implement example custom workflows.

1. Introduction

Computational methods and processing of Big Data in research are becoming progressively more important. Technological advancement yields increased precision of scientific instruments used in experimentation on the one hand, and better performance of the HPC infrastructure on the other hand. However, numerous technical challenges need to be overcome for the modern science to fully benefit from these advancements. One of these challenges is efficient and flexible data transfers. New generations of scientific instruments produce more and more data. Processing of that data requires a lot of compute power, which is usually available in HPC centers located far away from the data source. In addition, augmenting the experiments with numerical simulations also involves consumption and production of large amounts of data. Hence, efficient and smooth movement of data between distant locations is a crucial component of many scientific workflows. Here we consider the following technical aspects of moving data, which often arise in practice:

1. Efficient (high-bandwidth) transfer of the data over various distances
2. Pre- and post-processing of the data (e.g., archiving, compression, encryption)
3. Assuring data integrity on destination

The gap between bandwidth and computational performance has been steadily growing during the past decades. Consequently, in many cases the transfer of data from the instrument to the HPC facility, or transfer of the processed / simulation results from the HPC facility proves to be more time consuming than the computations themselves. This demonstrates the importance of being able to move data at or close to the peak available rates. Even then, many user groups are in practice forced to ship the physical hard drives to/from the HPC sites.

For large bulk transfers on short distances and with moderate network speeds the bandwidth can often be saturated using common TCP-based tools such as SSH, SCP, FTP, or rsync. Large distance transfers are more

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challenging: since TPC protocol requires verification of arrival of each data packet, the achievable bandwidth depends on the network latency. In other words, for a single TCP stream the bandwidth decreases with increasing Round Trip Time. There are two common solutions to this problem. Some tools use multiple parallel TCP streams to hide the network latency (e.g., GridFTP, bbcp, parsync, rclone, gsutil), others use a different network transfer protocol, e.g. UDP [1], which does not acknowledge each packet's delivery (e.g., GridFTP, netcat).

In all cases, bandwidth can only be saturated provided that the data streams are large enough, and transfer of a large number of small files is a bad idea. Although some tools like GridFTP try to improve the performance by re-using existing open network connections, such solutions are only partially effective, and cannot be used in all deployment scenarios due to firewall restrictions [2]. The consensus is that the files need to be packaged before transfer, and this duty always lies with the user. To automatize packaging and to relieve the user from having to increase the storage requirements by explicit creation of the archive, transfer tools often allow transmission of an in-memory data stream instead of a physical file. A standard way to achieve this on Unix systems is to read data from, or write data to a pipe (e.g., STDIN/STDOUT, or a named pipe). This mode is supported by e.g., globus-url-copy, netcat, SCP, or SSH. Another approach is to pass to the transfer tool a set of pre- or post-processing commands instead of a file list. The commands (e.g., tar, gzip, encrypt) are executed internally by the tool using the popen POSIX command. This solution is implemented in bbcp through named pipes, or in GridFTP through the Globus XIO Pipe Open Driver.

In most cases, it is required that the data is encrypted for transfer, and sometimes also for storage on the destination (e.g., sensitive data). Tools that rely on TLS for transfer, such as SCP, SSH, SFTP, rsync, provide transport level encryption and data integrity protection by default. In GridFTP and bbcp transport encryption and data integrity are optional and require command-line parameters. Netcat puts all responsibility on the user. None of these tools allow the user to easily store encrypted data on destination. In scenarios where this is required it has to be explicitly orchestrated by the user.

In some workflows, it is desirable to compute (and store in a separate file on the destination) a checksum of the transferred files. One example usage of this is to notify remote tools, which monitor the filesystem and wait for incoming data, about completed transfers. From the perspective of an independent observer running on the remote host it is impossible to know whether a given file transfer has completed, or whether it was interrupted half way, by only looking at the system state (e.g., incoming file size, or network connections). Indicating a successful transfer by creating an additional file containing a checksum of the data solves this problem. In addition, it also provides means for the user to verify data integrity after it has been written to disk. Similar functionality has been discussed in the context of the Globus XIO Pipe Open Driver [2]. In general, such feature is not natively supported by data transfer tools and has to be implemented by the users.

The choice of the data transfer tool depends on many factors such as performance in a given deployment scenario, but also usability and user authentication method. However, data preparation tasks discussed above are universal. The presented data transfer framework aims at providing a flexible and unified interface to the already available and established transfer tools. Its main objective is to prepare the data for transfer (e.g., tar, compress, encrypt, compute and verify hash), while delegating the network transfer to external utilities. The framework is based on the pipeline approach, i.e. the transferred data stream is passed through a sequence of pipeline elements (or 'filters'), which process the data and forward it downstream. The computations are done on the fly, hence there is no need for extra storage to archive and otherwise process the data. Compute-intensive tasks (e.g., compression, hash computations, encryption) are executed in parallel with the network transfer, which decreases the overall execution time of the whole workflow. The framework is implemented in Python3, hence it is portable and easy to extend: individual pipeline elements are similar to Python's file-like objects. We provide a general-purpose stager application driven by configuration files, and a Python API, which can be used to implement custom workflows.

2. Pipelined data transfer framework

Pipelined workflows

Preparation of the data for transfer (archiving, compression, etc.) is usually performed by the users themselves. Often the users create a tar-ball and transfer it to the destination using the tool of choice. UNIX users are familiar

with command-line processing of the data using pipelines: output of one program is passed as input to the next one using the pipe symbol '|', e.g.

```
tar -c src_dir | gzip | openssl enc -aes-256-cbc > tarball.enc
```

This example command creates a compressed and encrypted archive, and saves it to a file. Throughout the document we refer to the parts of the pipeline executed earlier as *upstream pipeline elements*, and the parts executed later – *downstream elements*.

Many existing data transfer tools can be used as a part of a standard UNIX command-line pipeline (e.g., GridFTP, SSH, netcat). Instead of saving the data to a local file, one can transfer it directly to a different host, e.g.

```
tar -cz src_dir | ssh user@host "tar -C dst_dir -xzf -"
```

In the above, the local tar command writes the compressed archive to the SSH connection, and the remote un-tar command reads data directly from the SSH connection. This solution is very flexible: there is a large library of data processing tools that can be readily used in customized pipelines.

Another approach is to pass to the transfer tools (e.g., GridFTP, bcp) a text argument that specifies the pipeline to be executed either on the source, or on the destination host. The tool internally executes the pipeline and consumes its results, or provides it with input data. This solution is more awkward to use, and may require some security considerations and system-level configuration (e.g., what commands should be allowed in a pipeline [2]), but it offers the possibility to remotely execute commands that prepare or stage the data, e.g.

```
bcp -N io 'tar -cz src_dir' remotehost:'tar -C dst_dir -xzf -'
```

In the above, bcp creates a tar stream on local host, sends it, and un-tars it at the destination by executing a remote tar command.

The presented work extends the idea of UNIX command-line pipelines to a programmable Python framework. The individual pipeline elements are implemented in Python3, which provides portability (the framework can be executed both on Windows, and on Unix machines). Custom pipeline elements can be implemented either in pure Python, or as *popen* calls to existing command-line tools, which allows for both re-use of the available software, and for easy implementation of functionality that is not available.

Figure 1. Example data preparation and transfer pipeline

Data flow and data processing model

The data processing is structured as a pipeline. An example, which will be often discussed in this paper, is shown in Figure 1. The pipeline is built from individual *pipeline elements*, which read the data from a preceding pipeline element, perform some operations internally, and forward the data to the following pipeline element. The internal

operations can, but don't need to process nor modify the data. The entire pipeline can be viewed as consisting of two parts:

- The *source pipeline* implements the part of data preparation that takes place before the network transfer, e.g., reading the data from the source (local or remote files, or a data stream), creating a tar archive, compressing, encrypting, computing the hash.
- The *destination pipeline* implements transfer of the data and any staging operations required on the destination, e.g., verifying the hash, decrypting, uncompressing, un-taring, and saving files.

In general, parts or all of the *source* and the *destination* pipelines can (but don't have to) be executed on different hosts. Hence, *source* and *destination* refer to the type of data processing, not to the place of execution. Consider the following usage scenario:

- transfer program is executed on Hosts 1
- source files are copied from Host 2 to Host 1 one at a time using, e.g., SFTP
- source files are packaged and compressed on Host 1
- archive is transferred to Host 3 using, e.g., SCP

In the above, while the data comes from Host 2, most of the *source pipeline* is executed on Host 1. The *destination pipeline* – transfer of data using SFTP - is also executed on Host 1, although the data is physically moved to Host 3.

Consider another scenario:

- transfer program is executed on Host 2
- source files are archived, compressed and encrypted on Host 1
- the prepared archive is transferred as stream to Host 2 over the SSH connection
- the archive is decrypted, uncompressed, and un-tared on Host 2

In the above, all data preparation tasks are executed on a remote Host 1, while the transfer itself is initiated, and the staging tasks are executed on the local Host 2.

In the current implementation, only locally executed pipelines are implemented in Python. Remote pipelines are constructed as a string that implements the needed UNIX pipeline, and are executed on the destination host using SSH, or are passed as an argument to the transfer tool (bbcp, or GridFTP). In the future, the framework will be extended to allow execution of Python pipelines on both local and remote hosts.

Advantages and disadvantages

The main feature of the pipeline approach is that the data is processed on-the-fly and in-memory, without the need to save the intermediate results to physical storage. There are several benefits to this:

- *Lower storage requirements.* Even if the original data can be compressed, the resulting archive can occupy a significant amount of space.
- *Fewer accesses to the storage device.* Datasets of several TB are usually stored on a network share. Unless the storage is connected through a high-speed link, such as Infiniband, reading and writing of data can be a severe bottleneck. Preparing the data in-memory removes the need for unnecessary read and write operations, and can significantly speed up the whole workflow.
- *Low memory consumption.* In a pipeline the data is processed incrementally and in small blocks. There is no need to keep the entire processed dataset in the memory. Only a small workspace is usually required.
- *Overlapping of execution time.* Pipeline elements work in parallel and process the data as soon as it is made available for reading by the previous pipeline element. Ideally, the total execution time is the maximum of the execution times of individual pipeline components instead of their sum.
- *Flexibility.* Pipeline elements can be easily added or removed, depending on particular needs.

A disadvantage of the pipeline approach is that, since the data being transferred is never stored wholly in a file, restarting a failed transfer is in general not possible. Instead, the entire pipeline has to be executed from the start, and all data may have to be re-sent. At this stage, we do not provide a solution to this problem. In general, it is possible to implement a session's mechanism that would allow to resume the network transfer from an arbitrary

position in the data stream. However, the pipeline itself may still need to be executed from the beginning, with the data already transferred being discarded instead of re-transferred. The main reason for this is that the available archiving tools (tar, zip) do not support sessions and restarts, and hence cannot continue from arbitrary interruption points.

Data integrity

On the low level, integrity of the data is addressed by the network transfer protocol: TCP and UDP packets contain a 16-bit checksum. However, this is considered weak by current standards. On a higher level, tools that rely on TLS automatically get the benefit of data integrity through a Message Authentication Code (MAC). This mechanism is very reliable and gives the receiver a certainty that the *individual messages* arrive from the sender unmodified. However, MAC does not assure completeness of the entire data stream.

As observed by the authors of bbcp [3], when one of the components in a pipeline for some reason indicates *end-of-file* (EOF), it is in general not possible for the downstream pipeline components to know whether this is caused by an error condition, or whether it actually indicates the end of the data stream. As a result, a data transfer may appear as complete, although in fact not all of the data has been transferred.

In the presented solution, this problem is addressed by a SHA256 compute and verification pipeline element. Its behavior depends on whether it is used in the *source*, or in the *destination* pipeline:

- In the source pipeline, it must be placed after the last element that modifies the data stream. It computes the SHA256 checksum of all data that passes through it. When EOF is received from upstream, it first writes the computed hash to the destination pipeline, and only then forwards the EOF. Thus, the computed hash is 'glued' at the end of the data stream.
- In the destination pipeline the hash element is the first element after the data transfer. It constantly buffers the last 32 bytes of the passing data assuming those are the 'glued' hash. It then updates the internal SHA256 computation and forwards the data (prepending the previously buffered 32 bytes, and without the last 32 bytes) downstream. When EOF is received from upstream, the most recently buffered 32 bytes are compared to the computed hash value, and an error is issued if they do not match.

If for any reason the transfer is terminated early, the last 32 bytes of the stream will contain part of the data stream instead of a valid hash. Hence, hash verification will fail and the receiving side will be able to take the necessary action.

Security considerations

Data transfers in general, and especially automatic data transfers without user interaction raise several questions regarding security. First and foremost, user authentication and authorization schemes should be considered. Since in this regards the presented framework relies on the underlying data transfer tools (e.g., GridFTP, SSH), it does not solve, nor add to the challenge.

A feature that does require security considerations is the remote execution of pipelines. When using bbcp or GridFTP-lite, SSH access to a remote host is required to start the remote instance of the tool. However, a full shell access is not necessary, and instead users may be granted key- or certificate-based access to the transfer tools only. Since both tools allow specification of the remote pipeline as an argument, in such deployment scenarios the pipelines must be validated to assure that the user is authorized to execute remote code. In case of GridFTP this is done through configuration files. On the other hand, bbcp does not put restrictions on the remote pipelines. This should be considered when deploying GridFTP or bbcp.

In situations when the remote UNIX pipelines are executed directly over SSH it is assumed that authorization to run the required commands is implied by user's access to the remote shell.

3. Implementation

Overview

The framework is implemented as a set of Python3 classes. From user's perspective, the most important are:

`conf.StageConfig` a structure populated with required configuration options related to data processing and transfer

`stage.streams.*` a collection of various useful pipeline elements

`stage.transfer.TransferManager` a driver class that executes the *source* and *destination* pipelines

Table 1 shows the supported options (fields inside `StageConfig` class), their meaning, and example supported values. Note that only the needed options have to be set. For example, if the source files are on the local machine (`src_proto=local`), `src_site` and `src_user` are not needed and will be ignored. The configuration structure is passed as parameter at each pipeline element's creation time, and each pipeline element extracts the relevant options (see Section *Available Pipeline Elements*).

The implemented pipeline elements can be accessed by importing the needed class from the `stage.streams` package. All concrete pipeline element classes must inherit from the abstract `BaseStream` class. The collection includes `FileLocal`, `FileSFTP`, `HashedStream`, `HashedFile`, `HashedFileVerify`, `TarLocal`, `TarCmd`, `EncryptedStream`, `DiskImage`, and `OutputMultiplexer`. Individual classes are described in Section *Available Pipeline Elements*.

The role of the `TransferManager` is to execute and monitor the transfer. The constructor's parameters are the last element of the *source* pipeline and the first element of the *destination* pipeline. Execution of the transfer essentially involves pumping of the data through the individual pipeline elements, in the direction from the *source* to the *destination* pipeline. To this end the `TransferManager` starts one OS process for each pipeline, i.e., *source* pipeline elements are executed by one process, and *destination* pipeline elements are executed by one process. The data is passed from the *source* pipeline to the *destination* pipeline using Python's `Pipe` class. This way the *source* pipeline process can pass data asynchronously to the *destination* pipeline process, and both processes can run in parallel.

There are two ways to use the data transfer framework. The first and simpler way is to use the provided general-purpose data stager. The other option is to implement a custom transfer script using the provided API.

Implementation of the example pipeline

As an illustration of the approach, consider the following Python code that implements the example pipeline from Figure 1.

```
# set configuration options
config          = StageConfig()
config.src_proto = 'local'
config.src_dir  = '/path/to/src'
config.dst_proto = 'ssh'
config.dst_site = 'example.site.com'
config.dst_dir  = '/path/to/dst'
config.package_type = 'tar'
config.compression = 'gzip'
config.hash      = 'sha256'
config.untar     = True

# create the source pipeline
is = FileLocal(config, 'r')
is = TarLocal(config, 'r', istream=is)
is = HashedStream(config, 'r', istream=is)

# create the destination pipeline
```

```
os = TarCmd(config, 'w')

# execute the transfer
tm = TransferManager(is, os)
tm.execute()
```

In the above code the *source* pipeline is implemented in Python and executed locally. Files are read recursively from a local directory (`FileLocal`) and added to a tar stream (`TarLocal`). The SHA256 hash of the compressed tar stream is computed and glued at the end (`HashedStream`).

The *destination* pipeline is executed remotely using SSH. The entire workflow is implemented in a single pipeline element (`TarCmd`), which constructs the UNIX shell command and executes it on the remote host. In the example case - based on the configuration options - the remote pipeline will verify the hash of the incoming stream and un-tar the files into the destination directory.

Notice that the pipeline elements are instantiated in *read* ('r') or *write* ('w') mode in the *source* and the *destination* pipeline, respectively. In general, the pipeline element objects instantiated from the implemented classes can be part of both the source, and the destination pipelines, but the behavior is different in both cases. For example, `FileLocal` can be located as the first element of the source pipeline, in which case it will act as a file reader (open the file, read data, close the file, proceed to next file). It can also be instantiated as the last element of the destination pipeline, in which case it will act as the file writer (create / truncate and open the file, write data, close file). The role of the elements (and hence the processing performed) is determined by the read/write mode parameter. For further details see section *Implementing custom pipeline elements*.

Attribute	Use	Supported values
src_dir	Path to the source directory	/path/to/source/directory
src_site	Source site hostname	Fqdn e.g. localhost, example.com
src_proto	Transfer protocol to be used for the source	local, sftp, ssh
src_user	Username with access at source site	e.g. andreas
file_include	Shell-style wildcards supported by Pythons fnmatch matching the files to include in the transfer	e.g. *.out
file_exclude	Shell-style wildcards supported by Pythons fnmatch matching the files to exclude from the transfer	e.g *.log
Data Destination		
dst_dir	Path to the destination directory	/path/to/dest/directory
dst_site	Destination site hostname	Fqdn e.g. localhost, example.com
dst_proto	Transfer protocol to be used for the destination	local, sftp, ssh
dst_user	Username with access at destination site	e.g. andreas
Data transfer pipeline		
package_type	Packaging algorithm	None, tar
package_name	Archive name (if saved)	e.g. out.tgz
compression	Compression algorithm	None, gzip, bzip2, xz
compresslevel	Compression level	1,2,3,4,5
work_dir	Working directory for temporary files (if needed)	/path/to/dir, e.g. /tmp
hash	Hash algorithm	None, sha256
untar	Defines whether the archive will be untared at the destination	boolean, default: False
hash_file	Defines whether a separate file containing the hash of each transferred file will be created at the destination	boolean, default: False
encrypt	Defines whether the dataset should be encrypted on source	boolean, default: False
decrypt	Defines whether the dataset should be decrypted on destination	boolean, default: False
Other options		
verbosity	Causes log messages to be printed	Integer [0..2], default: 0

Table 1. Available configuration options and their meaning.

Available pipeline elements

FileLocal

mode: r

configuration options: `src_dir`, `file_include`, `file_exclude`

Recursively searches local folder `src_dir` for files using Python's `os.walk`. Option `file_include` specifies a single wildcard to be matched using `fnmatch.filter`. Option `file_exclude` specifies a single wildcard to be matched using `fnmatch.fnmatch`.

A list of matching files is kept internally, with relative path under `src_dir`. The list is iterated by calling `FileLocal.open` with integer index. The `IndexError` exception is thrown for out of bounds indices.

The class estimates the total disk size required for the files by rounding the size of individual files up to a multiple of 4KB block size.

mode: w

configuration options: `dst_dir`

For each file name provided from upstream creates the local file under `dst_dir`. Files are created inside `FileLocal.open`, which takes the relative path under `dst_dir`, and file attribute `stat` structure as parameters.

FileSFTP

mode: r

configuration options: `src_site`, `src_user`, `src_dir`, `file_include`, `file_exclude`

Uses Paramiko [4] to connect to remote site using SFTP. Recursively searches remote folder `src_user@src_site:src_dir` for files using Paramiko's SFTP client. `file_include` specifies a single wildcard to be matched using `fnmatch.filter`. Option `file_exclude` specifies a single wildcard to be matched using `fnmatch.fnmatch`.

mode: w

configuration options: `dst_site`, `dst_user`, `dst_dir`

For each file name provided from upstream create the remote file under `dst_user@dst_site:dst_dir` using Paramiko's SFTP client. Files are created inside `FileLocal.open`, which takes the relative path under `dst_dir`, and file attribute `stat` structure as parameters.

TarLocal

mode: r

configuration options: `compression`

Uses Python's `tarfile` to create a compressed tar stream. The `compression` option can be one of `gzip`, `bz2`, `xz`, or `None`. This pipeline element iterates over the input objects using the `istream.open` function. For each input object a `tarfile.TarInfo` structure is populated and added to the tar stream using `tarfile.addfile`. After adding all input objects the tar stream is closed.

mode: w

configuration options: `compression`, `dst_dir`

Uses Python's `tarfile` to uncompress and untar the stream under destination directory `dst_dir`.

TarCmd

mode: r

configuration options: `compression`, `src_proto`, `src_user`, `src_site`, `src_dir`, `file_include`, `file_exclude`, `hash`

Depending on the options constructs and executes a UNIX shell pipeline, which creates a compressed tar stream. The shell command is currently executed either locally (`src_proto=local`), or remotely on `src_user@src_site` using SSH (`src_proto=ssh`). `compression` option can be one of `gzip`, `bz2`, `xz`, or `None`. Added files are located using UNIX command `find`, which uses `file_include` and `file_exclude` patterns. If `hash` option is specified, the produced tar stream is passed through an inline Python script that

computes the hash and glues it at the end of the stream. The final shell command is executed using Python's `Popen` interface.

mode: w

configuration options: `dst_proto`, `dst_user`, `dst_site`, `dst_dir`, `hash`

Depending on the options constructs and executes a UNIX shell pipeline, which untars a tar stream. The shell command is currently executed either locally (`src_proto=local`), or remotely on `dst_user@dst_site` using SSH (`src_proto=ssh`). compression option can be one of `gzip`, `bz2`, `xz`, or `None`. The tar stream is un-tared under destination directory `dst_dir`. If hash option is specified, the tar stream is first passed through an inline python script that computes the hash, and compares it to the last bytes of the stream that should contain the hash value. The shell command is executed using Python's `Popen` interface.

EncryptedStream

mode: r

configuration options: `None`

Encrypts the input stream using Python's `Crypto.Cipher.AES` in CBC mode. The encryption password and salt are passed as parameters to the constructor. If not passed, an empty password, and a random salt are used. The initial vector is computed from the salt and the password using MD5 sum in an iterative process, similarly to OpenSSL. The salt is prepended before the encrypted stream. The input stream is padded to the multiple of AES block size. Original stream size (8 bytes) is glued at the end of the stream unencrypted.

mode: w

configuration options: `None`

Decrypts the input stream using Python's `Crypto.Cipher.AES` in CBC mode. The encryption password should be passed as parameters to the constructor. The salt is assumed to be contained in the first bytes of the processed data stream. The initial vector is computed from the salt and the password using MD5 sum in an iterative process, similarly to OpenSSL. Last 8 bytes of the stream are unencrypted and contain the original stream size before padding. The bytes passed downstream are truncated to the original size.

HashedStream

mode: r

configuration options: `None`

Computes SHA256 hash of the input stream using Python's `hashlib`. The computed hash is glued at the end of the output stream.

mode: w

configuration options: `None`

Computes SHA256 hash of the input stream using Python's `hashlib`. To verify the data integrity the computed hash is compared to the last bytes of the input stream. `IOError` exception is raised if there is no match.

HashedFile

mode: r

configuration options: `None`

Computes SHA256 hash of the input stream using Python's `hashlib`. The computed hash is saved in a separate file on the destination. The hash file name is the same as that of the input stream with `.sha256` extension appended.

mode: w

configuration options: `None`

This class should not be used in 'w' mode. To verify the hash saved in a separate file use `HashedFileVerify`.

HashedFileVerify

mode: r

configuration options: None

Computes SHA256 hash of the input stream using Python's `hashlib`. Compares the computed hash to that stored in a separate file on the source. The hash file name must be the same as that of the input stream with `.sha256` suffix appended.

mode: w

configuration options: None

This class should not be used in 'w' mode.

DiskImage

mode: r

configuration options:

This class should not be used in 'r' mode.

mode: w

configuration options: `dst_proto`, `dst_user`, `dst_site`, `dst_dir`

Uses the disk images framework [5] to create and mount an EXT4 disk image on a remote host. The disk image is a file created at `dst_user@dist_site:dst_dir/imgname`, where `imgname` is a currently parameter passed to the constructor. The image is mounted under `/var/run/user_images/${dst_user}/import`. The `dst_dir` for the downstream pipeline elements is substituted to point to the image mount location. Hence, all imported files are saved inside the disk image. This is useful when saving a large number of small files on a network file system.

OutputMultiplexer

mode: r

configuration options: None

This class should not be used in 'r' mode.

mode: w

configuration options: None

Data obtained from upstream pipeline elements is sent to multiple downstream pipelines. The destination elements are added using the `add_ostream` method. An example usage of this is to save the data obtained from upstream to a local file, and at the same time save it to a remote backup host.

Execution of the pipelines

`TransferManager.execute()` function starts two processes using Python's `multiprocessing.Process`, one for *source* and *destination* pipelines. Each of the process pumps the data through the pipeline by executing the `stream` member function of a chosen pipeline element. The default `stream` function implementation from the `BaseStream` class is shown below:

```
def stream(self):

    # initialize io stream objects
    if self.mode[0] == 'r':
        istream = self
        ostream = self.ostream
    else:
        istream = self.istream
        ostream = self

    # iterate over input streams
    sid = 0
    while True:

        # open input and output 'files'
```

```

try:
    (location, st) = istream.open(sid)
    ostream.open(sid, location, st)
except (EOFError, IndexError):
    # end of list
    break

# copy bytes from istream to ostream
while True:
    b = istream.read(1024*1024)
    if b is None:
        continue

    # also write empty b buffer
    # to indicate EOF to the downstream elements.
    ostream.write(b)
    if len(b) == 0:
        break

self.close()
sid += 1

# cleanup procedure
self.finalize()

```

The outer-most loop iterates over all input objects provided by upstream: subsequent files are opened using a call to `istream.open` with a numeric index parameter. The most upstream element (`FileLocal`, or `FileSFTP`) opens the corresponding file from the list of files to be transferred, and returns its relative location and the `stat` structure with the file attributes. This information is passed downstream as arguments to `ostream.open`. This way the final pipeline element (e.g., `FileLocal`, or `FileSFTP`) knows where to store the data, and what attributes should the files have.

The inner-most loop pumps the data through the pipeline by reading blocks of bytes from `istream` and writing them to `ostream`. In Python's convention, an empty read from `istream` indicates EOF (end of file). Extending this convention, to indicate the EOF condition to the downstream elements an empty write must be performed. After that the streams can be closed.

All data processing performed by each pipeline element is implemented in the `read` and `write` functions. The computations depend on the mode, in which the pipeline element is opened (see Section *Available pipeline elements*). In special cases, pipeline elements must implement their own `stream` function. This is because it might not be possible to express the data processing in terms of calls to `read` and `write` functions that operate on blocks of data. For example, Python's `tarfile` archive cannot be written to or read from as a file-like object. Instead, `TarLocal` must iterate over input files in order to add them to the archive one by one. For more details see implementation of the `TarLocal` class.

General-purpose data stager

The general-purpose data stager (implemented in `stager.py`) is a command-line utility, which provides a general interface to the data transfer framework. Based on the provided configuration file the stager tool dynamically constructs the *source* and *destination* pipelines, and initiates the transfer by calling the `execute` method of the `TransferManager` class. Valid options for the configuration file are shown in Table 1.

The process of the *source* pipeline construction is illustrated in Figure 2. The process starts by identifying the source data access protocol. Currently supported protocols are `local`, `sftp`, and `ssh`. If the protocol is `ssh`, the pipeline is executed remotely as a UNIX shell command. Currently, the only class that supports pipeline execution over SSH is the `TarCmd` class, which can internally verify the hash glued to the stream, and untar files at given destination. If the source protocol is `local` or `sftp`, a native python pipeline is constructed and executed on the local host. Options defined in the configuration file are examined in the order shown in the flowchart, the

necessary pipeline elements are instantiated with the input stream set to the object instantiated as the previous pipeline element.

The dynamic construction algorithm of the *destination* pipeline is illustrated in Figure 2. Similar logic as with the *source* pipeline applies here. Depending on the options specified in the configuration file the required pipeline elements will be instantiated.

For better understanding consider the example configuration shown in Section *Implementation of the example pipeline*. The *source protocol* is set to *local*, *package_type*=*tar*, and *hash*=*sha256*. Following the flowchart, *FileLocal* class will be the first element of the source pipeline. Then, *TarLocal* will be instantiated, with its input stream being the previously instantiated *FileLocal* object. Finally, *HashedStream* will become the last pipeline element, and will be passed to the *TransferManager* as the reference to the *source* pipeline. Since the destination protocol is *SSH*, *TarCmd* object will be created for the entire *destination* pipeline.

Figure 2. Flow diagram of source and destination pipeline creation.

Implementing custom pipeline elements

All pipeline elements must inherit from the abstract `stage.streams.BaseStream` class. The constructor requires a configuration object, opening mode specification ('r' or 'w'), and optionally the preceding, or the next pipeline element (`istream/ostream`):

```
def __init__(self, config, mode, istream=None, ostream=None)
```

Pipeline elements are somewhat similar to Python's file-like objects in that they implement `open`, `close`, `read`, and `write` functions. The following are the default implementations provided in `BaseStream` class:

```
def open(self, sid, location=None, st=None):

    if location is None:
        self.location, self.location_st = self.istream.open(sid)
        return (self.location, self.location_st)

    self.location = location
    self.location_st = st
    return self.ostream.open(sid, location, st)

def close(self):

    self.closing = True
    if self.istream is not None and isinstance(self.istream, BaseStream):
        if not self.istream.closing:
            self.istream.close()
    if self.ostream is not None and isinstance(self.ostream, BaseStream):
        if not self.ostream.closing:
            self.ostream.close()

def read(self, nb):
    return self.istream.read(nb)

def write(self, bytes):
    return self.ostream.write(bytes)
```

By default, all those functions propagate the call to the preceding, or the next pipeline element. Concrete implementation should perform other required actions, e.g., `FileLocal` will open the actual file in the `open` function.

Custom implementations should consider that each of the above functions may in general be called either from the upstream, or from the downstream element. This is a result of how the `stream` function is implemented: for one chosen pipeline element in both the source, and the destination pipeline the stream function iteratively calls `istream.open`, `ostream.open`, `istream.read`, and `ostream.write`. Consider the `open` function. When called from a downstream element it takes an integer index, calls the upstream `istream.open`, and returns downstream the file name (`location`) and stat structure (`st`) obtained from upstream. In general, downstream elements do not know the file name, and instead iterate over all files using integer index. On the other hand, when `open` is called from upstream it takes the file location and stat structure as parameters, and forwards the call downstream to `ostream.open`.

Similarly, operations performed in `read` and `write` functions depend on the opening mode, and whether they are called from upstream, or from downstream. As an example, the following table summarizes the expected behavior of `read` and `write` functions of an `EncryptedStream` object depending on the opening mode (Table 2).

Since the data travels in the direction from upstream to downstream, and from the source to the destination pipeline, the `read` function can only be called from downstream elements, while the `write` function is only called from the upstream elements. When placed in the source pipeline an `EncryptedStream` object should encrypt the stream

in both `read`, and `write` functions. On the contrary, when the element is used in `'w'` mode the stream should be decrypted in both functions.

In some cases, it is impossible to express data processing in terms of reading, or writing blocks of data. One example is the `TarLocal` element, which uses Python's `tarfile` package. The `tarfile` archives do not provide file-like interface. In this case, it is necessary to implement a specialized `stream` function.

	'r' (source pipeline)	'w' (destination pipeline)
read called from downstream	encrypt data	decrypt data
write called from upstream	encrypt data	decrypt data

Table 2 Opening modes and corresponding actions of example source and destination pipeline elements.

Installation instructions

The procedure to install the framework on Linux is following below, but since the framework is purely implemented in Python3 it is compatible with Windows and MacOS as well. As a first step you need to obtain the latest version of the data transfer framework

```
git clone git@gitlab.com:marcin.krotkiewski/prace-instruments.git
```

Optionally, change to the newly created directory and create a virtual environment [6] with the Python3 interpreter by running

```
virtualenv -p python3 venv
```

It is recommended to use virtual environment to create an isolated Python environment for each of your python applications. To use the created virtual environment, you should activate it by sourcing the activate file

```
source venv/activate
```

The last step is the installation of the required Python modules: `paramiko` and `pycrypto`, which can be done using `pip`:

```
pip install paramiko
pip install pycrypto
```

General stager and configuration files

The general-purpose data stager is executed by running `stager.py`:

```
usage: stager.py [-h] config_file_name
```

Data staging tool

positional arguments:

```
config_file_name  configuration file name
```

optional arguments:

```
-h, --help          show this help message and exit
```

The script takes the configuration file name as the only command line argument. The configuration file should provide all the required information regarding the source and destination of the transfer, the directories and files to be transferred, the protocols used and the pipeline stages to be invoked in the data transfer. Configuration options are discussed in Table 1. Python's standard `configparser` package is used to read the configuration files. A sample configuration file, which implements the example pipeline from Figure 1 is the following:

```
[Defaults]
src_proto    = local
src_dir      = /path/to/src
dst_proto    = ssh
dst_site     = example.site.com
dst_dir      = /path/to/dst
dst_user     = john
package_type = tar
compression = gzip
hash         = sha256
untar       = True
verbosity   = 1
```

The first section defines the source's attributes, the second sections defines the destination's attributes, and the last section defines the data transfer parameters. Only the relevant attributes are needed to be set in the configuration file. The omitted attributes have the default values (Table 1). There is also the option to enable verbose output to have details about the transfer printed on the terminal.

The above configuration file implements the example pipeline: all files under `/path/to/src` are read and a compressed tar archive is created. The archive is passed through the SHA256 hash computation algorithm. The hash is appended at the end of the data stream. The data stream is sent through *SSH* to the `example.site.com` server as user `john`. As the data stream is received at the destination it is passed through the SHA256 hash computation algorithm and the archive is untared under `/path/to/dest`. As soon as the transfer is completed, the appended hash is compared with the computed hash at the destination to verify the integrity of the transferred data.

More example configuration files can be found in the source distribution, in folder `sample_configs`.

Custom transfer scripts

The framework has been used to implement several custom data transfer scripts specialized for particular scenarios. Those are in the `utils` directory:

- `cees_monitor`
- `tsd_put / tsd_get`

The following sections describe the functionality of these tools.

cees_monitor

This script is used at the *Centre for Ecological and Evolutionary Synthesis* (CEES) at the University of Oslo. The centre uses this script to automatically back up data produced by DNA sequencers, and to stage the data for computations at the local HPC facility.

```
usage: cees_monitor.py [-h] [--include INCLUDE] [--exclude EXCLUDE]
                    [-s SERVER] [-u USERNAME] [--untar] [--image] [-v]
                    src dst
```

CEES backup tool and monitor

positional arguments:

```
  src          input data location
  dst          directory on the destination server
```

optional arguments:

```
-h, --help          show this help message and exit
--include INCLUDE  file pattern to include when picking files from source
                  directory, default *
--exclude EXCLUDE  file pattern to exclude when picking files from source
                  directory, default None
-s SERVER, --server SERVER
                  destination server address (SFTP/ssh connection)
-u USERNAME, --username USERNAME
                  user name on the SFTP remote
--untar            uncompress files at destination
--image           uncompress files into a loop-back mounted disk image
                  on destination.
-v, --verbosity   print some runtime information
```

The tool runs an endless loop monitoring contents of `src` directory. For all subdirectories that it finds it checks whether they contain a special file indicating that a sequencer run has finished. If that is the case, `cees_monitor` constructs a pipeline that compresses the data and sends the archive to a backup SFTP server. A SHA256 file containing archive checksum is created on the destination.

Future versions of the script will use the `OutputMultiplexer` class to send the archive to the HPC facility for post-processing. Since the DNA sequencers notoriously produce large numbers of very small files, the script can use the `DiskImages` class to store the files inside a single file located on a network file system. This significantly improves the performance of both data staging (untar on destination), and processing (data access in compute jobs).

tsd_put / tsd_get

These custom scripts are used for data transfer into a secure computing facility for processing of sensitive data (*Tjenester for Sensitive Data* – TSD) located at the University of Oslo. The architecture of the system only allows SFTP access to a dedicated ‘border’ server (filelock). Users can only transfer their data into that machine. A dedicated program runs and monitors the incoming transfers. Complete uploads are forwarded further into the secure HPC facility. `tsd_put` is used on the outside to transfer the data into the facility:

```
usage: tsd_put.py [-h] [-d DST] [--enc] [--enc_salt ENC_SALT]
                [--enc_pass ENC_PASS] [-l COMPRESSLEVEL] [--include INCLUDE]
                [--exclude EXCLUDE] [-s SERVER] [-u USERNAME] [-v]
                src project import_name
```

TSD data staging tool. Source data is packaged using TAR+GZIP and sent to the remote server.

positional arguments:

```
  src          data to copy into TSD
  project      TSD project name
  import_name  user-defined name of the import.
```

optional arguments:

```

-h, --help                show this help message and exit
-d DST, --dst DST         local destination directory to copy into (if the
                           remote is locally mounted)
--enc                     Use AES encryption
--enc_salt ENC_SALT       salt used for encryption (public)
--enc_pass ENC_PASS       password used for encryption (secret)
--include INCLUDE         File pattern to include when picking files from source
                           directory, default *
--exclude EXCLUDE         File pattern to exclude when picking files from source
                           directory, default None
-s SERVER, --server SERVER
                           server address
-u USERNAME, --username USERNAME
                           user name on the SFTP remote
-v, --verbose             print some runtime information

```

The data is archived (tar+compress), optionally encrypted, and transferred using SFTP. A SHA256 file is created on the SFTP server that contains the archive hash. This indicates to the server-side monitoring program that the data transfer is complete. `tsd_put` supports *two-factor authentication* for enhanced security.

`tsd_get` is used on the inside of the secure compute facility to stage the data for computations:

```
usage: tsd_get.py [-h] [-s SRC] [--enc] [--enc_pass ENC_PASS] [-v]
                dst project import_name
```

TSD data staging tool: decrypt and unpackage archives imported into TSD.

positional arguments:

```

dst                destination directory, into which imported data should
                   be saved
project            TSD project name
import_name        user-defined name of the import.

```

optional arguments:

```

-h, --help                show this help message and exit
-s SRC, --src SRC         local source directory where imports are stored.
--enc                     Use AES encryption
--enc_pass ENC_PASS       password used for encryption (secret)
-v, --verbose             print some runtime information

```

This script locally decrypts and un-tars the previously imported archive.

Conclusions

We have designed and implemented a framework for automatic preparation and transfer of (large amounts) of scientific data. Its main objectives are:

- To prepare the data for transfer. This usually involves creating a compressed archive. In some common use cases encryption and hash computations are also necessary.
- To carry out the network transfer using established external utilities, such as gridFTP, bbcp, SCP, SFTP, and others.
- To monitor the transfer and notify the receiver about consistency and completeness of the data.

The framework is based on the well-known pipeline approach. Similarly to a UNIX shell pipeline, the data stream is passed through a sequence of pipeline elements (or ‘filters’), which read the data from the preceding element, process it, and forward it downstream.

There are several advantages of this approach. Since the computations are done on the fly, there is no need for extra storage to archive and otherwise process the data. This is important in many practical scenarios, especially when transferring large amounts of data. Moreover, compute-intensive tasks (e.g., compression, hash

computations, encryption) are executed in parallel with the network transfer, which decreases the overall execution time of the whole workflow. While the approach itself is not new and UNIX shell pipelines are commonly used, our framework is implemented in Python3, which makes it portable to other platforms (e.g., Windows), and applicable in more complicated deployment scenarios (e.g., Web applications). The framework is flexible when it comes to the data transfer protocol, and is easy to extend with new, custom pipeline elements. Finally, through a multiplexer pipeline element it is possible to send the prepared data stream to multiple destinations at once, e.g., save to a backup storage, and stage to an HPC facility for processing.

The main disadvantage at this stage is the fact that interrupted transfers cannot easily be resumed. This is a direct consequence of in-memory processing and the fact that a tar archive must be created incrementally, from the beginning to the end. We have proposed to extend the framework with a session-like capability to re-create the data stream on the sender side, discard the bytes that have already been sent, and resume the transfer from the interruption point. This remains to be done in the future.

References

- [1] B. Tierney and et.al., “Efficient Data Transfer Protocols for Big Data,” in *2012 IEEE 8th International Conference on E-Science*, 2012.
- [2] R. Kettimuthu and et.al., “Globus XIO Pipe Open Driver: Enabling GridFTP to Leverage Standard Unix Tools,” in *Proc. TeraGrid 2011*, 2011.
- [3] A. Hanushevsky, “BBCP,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.slac.stanford.edu/~abh/bbcp/>.
- [4] J. Forcier, “Paramiko. A Python implementation of SSHv2.,” [Online]. Available: <http://www.paramiko.org/>.
- [5] M. Krotkiewski, “Dealing with small files in HPC environments: automatic loop-back mounting of disk images,” PRACE, 2017.
- [6] “Virtual Environment homepage,” [Online]. Available: <https://virtualenv.pypa.io/en/stable/>.

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